

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

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Nandini Bhattacharya (PhD)

Associate Professor in History,
Calcutta Girls' College Kolkata –
700013 West Bengal India

THE PROCESS OF RECYCLE REUSE AND REDUCE AS AN ESSENTIAL SCIENTIFIC AWARENESS TO SUSTAIN THE ENVIRONMENT ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE MOVEMENT BEYOND FORMAL SCIENTIFIC EDUCATION ABSTRACT

Key words: Bottomline,
human

Abstract: Awareness about the sustenance of our planet is a scientific movement which touches each and all the members of this planet — human non-human living non-living all together as the resources as well as their users at the same however the cry to save the earth is being hard at each corner of this planet which begin to lose its balance and showing science of danger and decay around the last few decades.

ПРОЦЕСС ПЕРЕРАБОТКИ, ПОВТОРНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ И СОКРАЩЕНИЯ КАК НЕОБХОДИМАЯ НАУЧНАЯ ОСВЕДОМЛЕННОСТЬ ДЛЯ ПОДДЕРЖАНИЯ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ РОЛИ ЖЕНЩИН В ДВИЖЕНИИ ЗА ПРЕДЕЛАМИ ФОРМАЛЬНОГО НАУЧНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ АННОТАЦИЯ

Ключевые слова:
Нижняя граница , человек

Аннотация: Осведомленность о пропитании нашей планеты — это научное движение, которое затрагивает всех без исключения членов этой планеты — людей, нечеловеческих, живых, неживых, вместе взятых, как ресурсы, а также их пользователей одновременно, однако крик о спасении земли борется с каждым уголком этой планеты, которая начинает терять равновесие и демонстрирует науке опасность и упадок за последние несколько десятилетий.

Awareness about the sustenance of our planet is a scientific movement which touches each and all the members of this planet — human non-human living non-living all together as the resources as well as their users at the same however the cry to save the earth is being hard at each corner of this planet which begin to lose its balance and showing science of danger and decay around the last few

decades. It is the indiscriminate use and misuse of the planet and her resources that made human life endangered and the nature began to give strong signals of collapse when the awareness of environmental sustenance came up as a serious issue to address. The realisation of the collective survival or decay had been a common bottomline to fathom the fact that scientific knowledge is not enough to be restricted to laboratory experiments and higher mathematical break through, or even the IT revolution, but about the common human life and its consumption pattern. The values and morals that had undergone a thoughtless arrogance of 'use and throw', almost a slogan for rapidly growing consumerism had been somewhat halted by the unresolved question of waste management. And hence the slogan of 3rs or 4 rs are floated down and percolated into the common inhabitants of this world — a sense common responsibility is being generated to rescue the earth from the debries of its own used wastes.

Awareness about the sustenance of our planet is a scientific movement which is cutting through each and all the members of this planet human non-human living non-living all together as the resources as well as their users at the same however the cry to save the earth is being hard at each corner of this planet which begin to lose its balance and showing science of danger and decay around the last few decades. It is the indiscriminate use and misuse of the planet and her resources that made human life endangered and the nature began to give strong signals of collapse when the awareness of environmental sustenance came up as a serious issue to address. The realization of the collective survival or decay had been a common bottomline to fathom the fact that scientific knowledge is not enough to be restricted to laboratory experiments and higher mathematical break through, or even the IT revolution, but about the common human life and its consumption pattern. The values and morals that had undergone a thoughtless arrogance of 'use and throw', almost a slogan for rapidly growing consumerism had been somewhat halted by the unresolved question of waste management. And hence the slogan of 3rs or 4 rs are floated down and percolated into the common inhabitants of this

world — a sense common responsibility is being generated to rescue the earth from the debries of its own used wastes.

And this is where the role of women come up as one of the major contributors to this extremely necessary scientific endeavour. There had been series of studies and debates on the gender roles in the sustainability and waste management of the world. However, this paper would rather attempt to highlight where and how women simply have special advantages to contribute more in the process of recovering the earth from the danger of degeneration and collapse and how, in Spite of not being formally trained in scientific studies, they can offer their common knowledge and understanding and actively participate in the process of recycle, reuse and reduce (also re plant) to turn it a part of common consciousness of each members of this planet community.

Since this year is marked as a time to enhance and develop women's role in the scientific knowledge and methods, one can begin from the platform where women are already visible, aware or unaware about their role as volunteers of a scientific movement for saving mother earth.

The process of recycle reuse and reduce as an essential scientific awareness to sustain the environment role of women in the movement beyond formal scientific education

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